

MAGNETIC EVIDENCE REGARDING THE STATE OF METALLIC IONS IN PHOSPHATE GLASSES.

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The nature of the polyvalent ions in phosphate glasses, especially Mn, Co and Ni has been investigated. The manganese in the reduced colourless glasses is in a bivalent state of combination. The pink-violet colour of manganese glasses is due to trivalent manganese ions. Cobalt ions do not suffer any change on reduction. The blue colour of cobalt glasses and the yellow colour of nickel glasses are attributed to bivalent cobalt and nickel respectively and when the latter are reduced, the glass becomes opaque due to the formation of metallic nickel.

There has been much speculation as regards the agents responsible for the colours of various precious stones and minerals. Manganese has long been supposed to be the source of the colour of the amethyst (Berthelot, *Compt. rend.*, 1906, **143**, 477), although the latest evidence attributes the colour to iron rather than to manganese. According to Sir Herbert Jackson (*Nature*, 1927, **120**, 303) none of these views is conclusive. Mellor ("A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1935, VI, 523) states that manganese colours alkaline glasses pink to violet under oxidising conditions. According to Thorpe ("Dictionary of Applied Chemistry", 1912, II, 721) the full colour is only developed when manganese is in a fully oxidised condition (Mn^{IV}). In Fuwa's opinion (*J. Japan Ceramic Assoc.*, 1923, **366**, 80) the manganic oxide is responsible for the pink colour and bivalent manganese for the decolorised glass.

Notable contributions on the subject have been made by Bancroft and Nugent (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 481), Solomin (*Keram. i. Steklo*, 1932, **8**, iii, 28), Childs and co-workers (*J. Soc. Glass Tech.*, 1931, **15**, 172), Turner and Weyl (*ibid.*, 1935, **19**, 208), Hoffmann (*Glass*, 1926, **13**, 419, 423, 433) and others. Bancroft, while studying manganese-borax beads from the point of view of their oxygen availability, has concluded that the pink-violet colour is due to trivalent manganese present probably in the form of free manganic oxide, and that the manganese in the colourless reduced glass is bivalent and is in combination as manganous borate. An attempt has been made by us to clarify the issues by the aid of magnetic susceptibility measurements, since the magnetic susceptibilities of ions of an

element in different states of valency can be calculated on the well known Stoner and Van Vleck formula,

$$\chi_m = \frac{N\beta^2}{3kT} [4S(S+1) + L(L+1)]$$

where values of S and L are determined by the valency state of the element. A preliminary note on the subject has been published by one of us (Bhatnagar, *Nature*, 1939, **143**, 559) and it has been shown that manganese in the decolorised borax and phosphate glasses is bivalent and that in the coloured one is a mixture of bi- and trivalent states. The nature of the colorant ions in phosphate glasses, especially manganese, which could not be established, has been thoroughly investigated and a study of nickel and cobalt glasses has also been included in the present investigation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The melts were made from pure crystallised microcosmic salt in an electric furnace which could be made muffle or open to the atmosphere at will. MnO_2 made by heating analytically pure $Mn(NO_3)_2$ was used. The melts were reduced with ashless tartaric acid to colourless state in the closed muffle. Other ions in turn were also introduced in the blank glass as pure oxides. Platinum dishes were used to avoid entry of all possible impurities. The colour conditions of the melts could be determined at any moment by taking out a bead on a platinum wire. The melts prepared were cooled in a desiccator and finely powdered in an agate pestle and mortar before the susceptibility measurements were made on a magnetic balance of the Guoy type.

Analysis of Glasses.

Manganese.—In order to determine accurately the amount of manganese in the various melts, a slight modification had to be made in the bismuthate method reported by Park (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1926, **18**, 597). It was found that the presence of phosphates from the glasses hindered the estimation of manganese and therefore the phosphates were removed by treating the aqueous solution of the glass with 12½% NaOH and 30% H_2O_2 followed by boiling when manganese was precipitated as an impure hydrated oxide free of the phosphate and could be filtered off on a sintered glass filter.

The precipitate thus obtained was dissolved in acidified FeSO_4 , excess of which was converted to ferric sulphate with H_2O_2 whose excess, in turn was destroyed by boiling. Solution thus prepared was treated with sodium bismuthate and the manganese estimated from the resulting permanganate.

Cobalt.—The presence of phosphates was found to interfere in the estimation of cobalt as well by the α -nitroso- β -naphthol method and they had to be removed by first oxidising cobalt to cobaltic oxide with 30% H_2O_2 in presence of 12½% NaOH. This could then be dissolved in hydrochloric acid and estimated.

Nickel—Nickel was estimated by the dimethylglyoxime method which worked successfully even in the presence of the phosphates.

Several melts of the blank glass were prepared under different conditions of length and nature of heating and cooling and their susceptibilities were checked against those of KCl and NaCl, values of which are definitely known. The susceptibility values of the various blank glass melts were all within experimental error (-0.389 to -0.391×10^{-6}). The average value -0.390×10^{-6} was taken for calculating the ionic susceptibilities given in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Reduced colourless manganese glasses. (30°)

No.	Mn.	χ_{Glass} .	χ_{Mn} (ionic).
1.	1.265%	2.916×10^{-6}	261.0×10^{-11}
2.	2.150	5.213	260.2
	2.413	2.925	261.0 Mean 260.7

TABLE II.

Coloured manganese glasses. (25°).

No.	Mn.	χ_{Glass} .	χ_{Mn} (ionic).	No.	Mn.	χ_{Glass} .	χ_{Mn} (ionic).
1.	1.40%	3.144×10^{-6}	252.10×10^{-11}	4.	2.36%	5.593×10^{-6}	253.1×10^{-11}
2.	1.99	4.580	249.3	5.	2.61	6.236	253.5
3.	2.10	4.870	250.0	6.	3.63	8.824	253.4
				7.	3.90	9.390	250.3

TABLE III.

Cobalt glasses (without reduction, 30°).

No.	Co.	χ_{glass} .	$\chi_{\text{co(ionic)}}$.	No.	Co.	χ_{glass} .	$\chi_{\text{co(ionic)}}$.
1.	1'231%	$1'710 \times 10^{-9}$	$170'2 \times 10^{-9}$	3.	2'33	$3'572 \times 10^{-9}$	$169'6 \times 10^{-9}$
2	2'271	3'474	169'7	4.	3'30	5'225	169'7

TABLE IV.

Cobalt glasses (reduced, 20°). Nickel glasses (without reduction, 20°).

No.	Co.	χ_{glass} .	$\chi_{\text{co(ionic)}}$.	No.	Ni.	χ_{glass} .	$\chi_{\text{co(ionic)}}$.
1.	1'325%	$1'866 \times 10^{-9}$	$169'9 \times 10^{-9}$	1.	1'148%	$0'336 \times 10^{-9}$	$80'20 \times 10^{-9}$
2.	2'010	3'034	170'1	2.	2'689	1'778	80'21
3.	2'428	3'739	169'5	3.	3'316	2'276	80'00

TABLE V.

Calc. values of ionic susceptibilities on Stoner-van Vleck formula $\times 10^9$

Temp.	Mn ⁺⁺	Mn ⁺⁺⁺ L-not operative.	Mn ⁺⁺⁺ L-operative.	Co ⁺⁺ L-not operative.	Co ⁺⁺ L-not operative.	Ni ⁺⁺ L-operative
30°	260'6					
25°	265'3	181'9	227'3			
20°				107'7	193'8	57'72
						144'3

DISCUSSION.

Manganese Glasses.

Calculating the ionic susceptibilities of manganese from the Stoner-Van Vleck formula for bivalent manganese, which is in the 6S state, the orbital moment L equals zero, the spin moment S has a value $5/2$, and the ionic susceptibility at 30° works out at $260'6 \times 10^{-9}$. This value is in close agreement with mean value of $260'7 \times 10^{-9}$ obtained experimentally in Table I. The decolorised glass when viewed in the ultraviolet light from a mercury vapour lamp with a Wood's filter, showed an orange-red fluorescence, identical with that of the anhydrous manganous halides. These observations prove that manganese in the colourless glass is in bivalent state of combination.

As regards the coloured manganese glasses it has been believed by most workers that it is the trivalent manganese which is responsible for the pink-violet colour. The trivalent manganese is in 6D_0 state. Spin moment L also is 2. It has been noted by Sommerfeld ("Atombau", 4th Ed p. 639), Bose (*Z. Physik*, 1927, **43**, 864), Stoner (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, **8**, 250) and others that for ions of the iron group, the L -moment is fully quenched and its value is zero. Calculating on this basis we find that the ionic susceptibility for trivalent manganese works out to 181.9×10^{-6} at 25° . If the orbital moment were not quenched, the other limiting value for fully operative L -orbital moment is 227.3×10^{-6} . As shown in Table II the experimental values range between those of the bivalent (265.3×10^{-6} at 25°) and trivalent states. This gives one good reason to believe that it is a mixture of the bi- and trivalent manganese compounds which is responsible for the various shades of colour.

To find out how much exactly of each state is present, available oxygen in the first five samples of Table II was found out. For this purpose a certain weight of the glass (2.5 to 3.0 g.) was covered in an Erlenmeyer flask with a known excess of standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution, and left to dissolve gradually. When the glass completely disappeared the quantity of the reducing agent consumed was found out and the available oxygen calculated from it. To avoid errors of oxidation by the atmosphere a blank was always titrated alongside and use of heat for quickening the solution of glass was avoided.

TABLE VI.

No.	Manganic ions in total Mn.	χ_{ionic} (calc.)		χ_{ionic} (obs).
		L-operative.	L-quenched.	
1.	14.5%	259.5×10^{-6}	253.2	252.1×10^{-6}
2.	15.2	259.2	252.5	249.3
3.	13.1	259.9	254.2	250.0
4.	12.6	260.2	254.5	253.1
5.	12.7	260.1	254.4	253.5

As is clear from Table VI, the observed values of susceptibility of the manganese ions are in fairly good agreement with the calculated ones for a mixture of manganous and manganic ions. L -orbital moment being fully quenched for the manganic ions. Since we have found that the bivalent manganese gives colourless glass, it must be the trivalent ions which are responsible for the pink-violet colour,

Cobalt Glasses.

It is a well known fact that when cobalt-borax or microcosmic beads are exposed to the reducing flame there is no change in colour. The susceptibility values given in Tables III and IV for the glass, made in free excess of air and one reduced with tartaric acid, are practically identical. This confirms that there is no change in the nature of cobalt ions. Furthermore these susceptibilities are intermediate between the two limiting values calculated for the bivalent cobalt ions shown in Table VI, which must be responsible for the blue colour of the cobalt glasses.

Nickel Glasses.

Nickel was found to colour the phosphate glasses yellow. The ionic susceptibilities found for nickel ions as given in Table IV are between the limits calculated for the bivalent nickel with *L*-moment operative and quenched. This indicates that the yellow colour is due to the bivalent nickel ions. When nickel glasses were reduced with tartaric acid, they yielded an opaque mass which was ferro-magnetic in nature and indicated presence of metallic nickel.*

* These values observed by us for bivalent cobalt and nickel ions in the phosphate glasses are in line with those obtained by Bhatnagar, Khana and Nevgi (*Phil Mag*, 1938, 8, 250) for certain other salts of cobalt and nickel.